

TRADITIONAL ART IN MODERN FINE ARTS: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON EDUCATION VALUE

***BUDIWIRMAN, SYEILENDRA, AGUSTI EFI, ZULFA and IFDIL**

*Email: budiwirman1959@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Traditional arts that seem to have high artistic value must always be preserved from extinction. To sustain the popularity of traditional arts in Indonesia, artists, teachers, and people with a deep understanding of them are required. Adopting modern arts is among the most key strategies to maintain traditional arts and values. Besides from that, every fine art artist must have a feeling of nationalism. In addition, a unique education system must be created to teach and train young artists in this process. In order to keep up with abstract expressionism, it is also required to make changes to art education in the context of curriculum, input, and output.

Key words: Fine art, high artistic, have education, culture, beautiful art.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional art is found inside one place and becomes deeply ingrained in the mind of a certain set of people and community (Huhmarniemi & Jokela, 2020). Traditional art's cultural values are revered as ancestors' legacy (Sulistyanto, 2019). (Park, Hwang, Lee, & Heo, 2020), traditional art displayed in public places tend to maintain its originality. (Bublitz et al., 2019) stated that traditional art is highly valued and needs to be preserved because it is the pride of a group of people. The cultural values of a community is greatly admired and respected as the ancestral heritage, therefore, all forms, contents and rhythms do not need to change (Bentley & O'Brien, 2017; Tacon, 2019). The traditional art displayed in public tends to appear the same because it maintains originality (Graburn, 2021). Furthermore, those owned by Indonesians are in diverse forms, which make the country rich in artistic products. These forms of art include traditional ceremonies, painting, sculpture, graphic arts, crafts, dance, sound art, etc (Ismail, Nggilu, & Tome, 2019).

The results of the cultural arts of Indonesians are very diverse in appearance and shape (Setiawan & Handojo, 2017). Tribes such as Minangkabau, Javanese, Sudanese, Batak, Balinese, Irianese, and Nias have different customs and traditions. According to Yuwono et al. (2020), Indonesia is rich in artistic product due to its diversity in traditional arts through various ceremonies, painting, sculpture, graphic arts, craft, dance, and sound art.

Generally, a group of people that perform traditional arts mostly live far from the hustle and bustle of the city to avoid being influenced by outside culture. They acquire skills and experience from their parents, the surrounding community, ancestors, and scratches long kept in museums. Several studies have found arts as the major supporter of people area community. Therefore, development, preservation and analysis of traditional art needs to be developed to preserve and appreciate these works (Jian et al., 2019).

The results of many traditional arts have creative products that are pleasing to the eye. However, those that create these arts lack commercial and competitive elements because these works of art are designed as devotion to traditional arts. The teacher or practitioner of art education plays an essential role in the evolution of traditional to modern era.

Fine arts educators have a great responsibility in commercializing art products (Kenning, 2019). In Indonesia, the act of teaching fine arts education is applied from elementary school to higher education. Fine arts education is very important in improving the quality and quality of art, although it is often a major or science of interest because it does not guarantee individual welfare with a straightforward job (Kenning, 2019). Due to the love for art, some professionals with productive occupations, migrate into the study of art from science (Kenning, 2019).

According to (Allen & Rowles, 2016), experts in the field of art, find it challenging to open special art schools or carry out private art courses both at the undergraduate program level and at the postgraduate level. Currently a certain percentage of artists have earned £5,000 from their activities (Harper, 2014). For arts to be professional in their field, they need to have the courage to present themselves to the outside world (Allen & Rowles, 2016) and seek opportunities to be known by many people (Kenning, 2019).

Art education develops traditional art into modern art in this modernization era. According to a research carried out by Thom (2017) on art lecturers in England and Germany using entrepreneurship education, art education curriculum, consists of training to develop entrepreneurial mindset, skills, personal development planning, real-life scenario teaching, longer and more work placements/study visits, with focus on engaging galleries, customers, banks, audiences, and exchanging forum for creating demand.

The curriculum is market-oriented and entrepreneurship, the lecturers provide learning techniques, such as “art survival training” (Thom, 2017). This is also in line with the purpose of art education carried out to creatively gain knowledge and skills on arts and culture of the society (Clarke & Hulbert, 2016). This curriculum recommends the use of learning to prepare students and aspiring artists to get realistic job descriptions simulated through trainings and playing the roles (Thom, 2017).

In addition, art education needs to be applied at the level of education because it has numerous benefits in terms of goal setting, self-confidence, commitment, stress reactions, fear control, relaxation, activity, focus and mental training (Uzun Dönmez & Imamoglu, 2020). Clarke & Hulbert (2016) stated that participants have the ability to prepare creative art education graduates (Clarke & Hulbert, 2016). Fine arts education needs to be able to reveal the uncertainty and open nature of creative production. The goal is to ensure students are successful in cultivating themselves, by being creative with academic aspirations (Shreeve, 2009). In addition, to develop visual arts education, teachers need to replace traditional learning methods with the modern types (Sun, 2021). of the traditional art of learning models, need to be integrated into new forms with adequate data field modes for high-quality talent development (Sun, 2021). Individuals at the stage of carrying out art education, need to

introduce collaborative art for creativity in developing modern art such as mural works (Golden, Scobey, Rice, & Kinney, 2002). Research carried out by Gama et al. (2018) found that traditional art produces products that can be commercialized in various tourist objects.

There are many policies that have been put in place to preserve traditional arts, such as students the teaching of art subjects and education in schools. According to Cvetkova et al. (2010) fine art products affect students' active knowledge. This is because the composition of art as a combination of various elements of art analyzes an artistic composition (Cvetkova, Andonovska-Trajkovska, & Atanasoska, 2010). Some majors in art education, such as the music and arts departments, require encouragement, and intervention to achieve educational satisfaction (Demirbatır, 2020). The study found that the art education style proposed is an acceptable way to transfer peoples' thinking patterns from the visual arts, especially new and participatory media arts, to determining solutions to the society (Vuk & Bosnar, 2021). The principles of learning fine arts are communication skills training, with the development of modern online art education (Li, 2021). According to (Vuk & Bosnar, 2021) fine arts education changes the paradigm of learning pure art to a more process-oriented method. The act of transferring this process, is necessary to connect students' creative activities with the context of everyday life (Vuk & Bosnar, 2021).

Sedyawati, (1995), there is need for a spirit of nationalism in fine arts, because this word fights for and maintains independence, prosperity and other interests of a nation. Followers of such movements are called nationalism. In this period of development, which is being promoted by the government a sense of nationalism is still absolutely necessary. Furthermore, with the widespread influence of science and technology from developed countries, it is critical for the world of fine arts to be narrowed and eventually become extinct.

These extinctions are commonly found in the traditional art, which decline in terms of quality and quantity due to illegal sells. Therefore to save the declining quality of art, the services of educated and skilled artists need to be effectively employed by the government. Questions associated with the right person to save these traditional art works from declining and extinction with a nationalist spirit arises.

The characteristics of an artist with a nationalist spirit need to reflect on the cultural values of the Indonesian people. These characteristics are in accordance with the technical issues as well as the content, mission and style associated with the artist. According to Kusnadi (1974), traditional art is divided into 4 parts, namely, painting, sculpture art, handicraft and modern art.

Method

This research was conducted using qualitative research with ethnographic methods. Research with ethnographies or ethno methodology describes the cultural characteristics of a group of people or individuals in a cultural group (Hanurawan, 2016; Johnson & Christensen, 2019). The cultural analysis carried out is on traditional painting, traditional sculpture art, traditional handicraft and traditional value. The regional cultures that are analyzed are West Sumatra,

South Sulawesi, Bali, and Irian Jaya. The subjects of this research are cultural experts in each of these areas. Analysis of the data used using the Sprawled model.

Result and Discussion

Traditional Painting

Paintings on caves in South Sulawesi (Brumm et al., 2021; Muda & Susant, 2020; Thosibo, Soekamto, Duli, & Mulyadi, 2019) and Irian Jaya (Nasrudin, 2017), Graphics on palm leaves in North Sumatra and Bali (I. D. A. D. Putra & Abdullah, 2020), Wayang beber in Java (Arya Pageh, 2018; Pujiono, Priilosadoso, & Supeni) and Balinese puppet carvings in Kames an (I. D. A. D. Putra, 2018) are examples of traditional paintings.

Figure 1: Painting in Goa

Based on the elution absorption and color reactions results, paints of red and black are not derived from human or animal blood. Furthermore, the analysis results showed that the main content of all paint paintings from different locations is CaO and SO₃. This indicates that the measured paint contains a lot of lime and other chemical components such as reddish brown Fe₂O₃. (Muda & Susanti, 2020; Thosibo, et al., 2019), this compound contributed to the red, brown and black paintings.

TRADITIONAL SCULPTURE ART

Examples of traditional sculpture art are statues of ancestors in various islands and reliefs in temples located in Java and Bali (Metusala, Lestari, Damaiyani, MAS'UDAH, & SETYAWAN, 2020; Nuruddin, Wirawan, Pantiyasa, Semara, & Estikowati, 2020; I. D. Putra & Abdullah, 2019).

Figure 2: Sculpture at the Temple

TRADITIONAL HANDICRAFT

Traditional handicraft are objects used to analyze the cultural/aesthetic aspects of ceremonies in Indonesia. Some of these objects include weaving art, batik motifs with certain symbolic meanings, and wood carving for decorating religious buildings, such as mosque. Decorative motifs are seen on ceramic objects, such as those used for drinking water, save money and go shopping.

Figure 3: Sculpture at the Temple

Traditional art has two evaluation directions namely national and international cultural expression and personality as well as an economic problem to improve the welfare of people. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the authors to develop a traditional art system capable of applying the cultural and social systems in nature. Besides the official bodies that are managed by the government also stated that modern art is a work creatively designed and free from the norms or methods of traditional art. Furthermore, the work produced is universal, therefore, sometimes people find it difficult to understand the paintings in the form of art.

The reviews of this study were analyzed from national and international perspectives. Therefore, these are in accordance with the studies carried out by Yustino (1995) titled "Fine Arts," was full of life force, in accordance to the birth of impressionism (1874) (Clever, 1967), Post Impressionism (1886) (Tompkins Lewis, 2007), Fauvism (1995) (Smith, 2002), Futurism (1909) (Berghaus & Berghaus, 1996; Slataper, 2020), Expressionism (1905) (Rampley, 2021), Cubism (1907) (O'Brien, 2018), and Surrealism (1924) (Soedjono, 2019). From then on, individual freedom truly gained the widest possible place with each artist allowed to compete and gain experience nationally and internationally.

With the rapid development in the field of science and technology, which has ruled the world, art life increasingly feels dragged. Therefore, various artists are restlessly thinking of ways to save aesthetic values that have been partially shifted by values that were born from reason, such as science and technology. Artists are responsible for creating new works in terms of technical ideas.

Besides these artists always displays ideas in public during exhibitions and festivals, to gain a place in the heart of the general public and recognition from critics. They carried out this process of pure art, for the society. It is natural to live in this modern age, which basically is all materialist and individualist life, each artist competing with one another for individual

recognition. Sometimes, these artists forget the aesthetic values of the traditional arts of their region because they believe their supporters are the wider community. This reaction arises in a form of fine art as a reaction to the value of old and most modern art. Creative artists always think broadly, dialogue and discuss with people, read a lot to acquire more knowledge about art theories, and carry out numerous experiments.

TRADITIONAL VALUES IN MODERN ART

Artists are always looking for ways to create new things, and sometimes forget to care for the artistic values surrounding them. For instance, they sometimes forget to show coastal captive and martial arts of brides during wedding ceremony. This is in addition to their inability to adhere to the values of the tradition; rather they preferred the popular modern arts, such as Jazz, Rock, Disco, Rolling Stone, Vina Panduwinata and Euis Darliah.

Similarly, in traditional art artists completely forgot the antique chairs from Jepara, which is the original songket woven cloth from Pandai Sikek and Silungkang with food. They also forget to decorate ashtrays carved with motifs typical of Bali or Irian. It is also possible for these artists to forget the availability of writing stones and Bundo Kandung's house because they are more interested in Mondrian, Henri Matisse, Pablo Picasso, and Jackson Pollock paintings. This is in addition to the statue of Naum Gabo, Henri More or Constant in Brancusi seen from books and photocopied for resume assignments at the UNP Padang Fine Arts Department.

For instance, a group of young artists were exposed to a great dilemma between choosing from traditional values or external values being pumped by lecturers. These scientists came from abroad through books or magazines on aesthetic science which is new and needs to be known by modern artists today. Artists need to be aware that they are native Indonesian nation required to serve the country and nation. Therefore, the works created by these workers, reflects on their motifs or forms of tradition that they enjoys. Are the motifs that are found in traditional Minangkabau, Batak, Balinese (Dibia & Ballinger, 2012) etc, or describe the movements of traditional dances such as plate dance, srimpi, pendet, golek, braid horse and others, (Budiwirman, 2018).

Technically, it is not necessary to bound art by realistic forms, rather to be free according to their individual tastes and pleasures irrespective of their expressionist style, such as Expressionist, Cubism, even Abstract forms which are basically themed Indonesian traditional art. Abstract visual art which acts as the scourge of conversation presumably is no longer an issue because it is clear that abstraction forms have been pioneered by the ancestors of the Indonesian people. Abstract motifs have been appreciated in the use of wood fiber motifs on the keris framework which are proud of as an element of beauty. Artists that participate in nationalism, from traditional art which are raised to modern forms with the values determined within days. They carry regional flags which are essentially the culture of the original Indonesian nation also found in other countries. Therefore, these works are appropriately termed Traditionalism-style art, which means the art that in its contents and meaning reflects or depicts the values of the nation's cultural traditions. They are able to

combine the essence of the past arts growing in the community. Therefore, the works that arise can be accepted by the people with future penetration. Irrespective of its exhibition region, people would still call it Indonesian art. This is because it uses similar forms and techniques, such as naturalism, impressionism, abstract, or decorative as long as all of them get a quality solution. The traditional works of senior art groups have been pioneered, to visualize paintings of Batara Lubis, Irsam, Popo Iskandar, Hatta Hambali, Nyoman Gunarsa, and Suwaji. This is in addition to the abstract sculptures by Sunaryo, and the decorative Sapto Hudoyo. Similarly, the group of young artists that are now starting to be intrigued need to provide guidance to a more perfect direction. Adequate physical and technical skills are needed to acquire the traditional values of art. This is in addition to the ability to think sharper in determining new values. For this reason, a fine arts education institution is needed to deliver and educate successive cadres to save traditional artistic values that have start declining in terms of quality and extinction. These cadres later become good-looking authors, educator artists, creators, craftsmen, managers and observers.

BEAUTIFUL ART RESEARCHER

The first possibility is the authors' senses of responsibilities to explore research and develop scientific knowledge of art. They are expected to become figures of fine art scientists capable of being accounted for their ideas and experimental findings. Furthermore, their knowledge has been structured scientifically, therefore, when the findings are communicated to the public, it is welcomed with utmost satisfaction (Finley & Knowles, 1995; Sullivan, 2010).

BEAUTIFUL ART EDUCATORS

The second possibility is good-looking art educators with the ability to educate, foster and apply the values of art to future generations. However, in most cases the educators are challenged with adjusting to the conditions of the times, therefore they need to actively develop themselves at all times. An educator must have extensive knowledge for easy understanding during teaching, to avoid confusion. Educators in fine arts cannot give an ultimatum towards certain styles, rather they only direct and provide suggestion, for the continuous development of the creative potential of students with new ideas.

BEAUTIFUL ART CREATOR

There are numerous good-looking art creators and designs that can be designed by artists and expected to function as reformers. Similarly, as a creator of fine art patterns, it is expected to be in harmony with national interests. Beautiful art creator of design is expected to be able to bring old values that are adapted to the needs of the society. It needs to be able to balance the flow of science and technology which corners the narrow aesthetic values of angles. This is to ensure the provision of new designs to meet the needs of life in harmony with the interests of the people and countries that are the pride of the nation.

ARTISAN SHAPELY CRAFTSMAN

It is necessary to have shapely art craftsman with high skills and the ability to understand design in order to reproduce and disseminate art for the public.

BEAUTIFUL ART MANAGER

Beautiful art managers are responsible for the preservation of arts. They strive to design and drive art in accordance with the GBHN developed by government and private bodies, such as the department of education, Industry, Tourism, Trade, Transmigration, Cooperatives and research bodies. Museums are very supportive in the preservation of art works and acts as a barometer of art life and an answer to future generations of results achieved in the past.

BEAUTIFUL ART OBSERVER

A creator of fine art is also called a beautiful art observer. This category of people, are always responsive and observe developments in art with moral responsibility, and ability to cast opinions, ideas and criticisms of a work of art, which is conveyed to the public through mass media and discussion forums (Schulz & Hayn-Leichsenring, 2017). The set of beautiful art that has been mentioned earlier are all supporters of the Indonesian art ideals willing to incorporate traditional cultural values into a modern art form in line with current advancements. In other words, they are beautiful figures capable of carrying old cultural values as the basis for creating modern art.

The results of this art are very amazing and fascinate people. This is because there has never been a commercial element and competition between individuals. Their satisfaction is only in the inner soul of a deep sense, because they contribute energy and thought in the interests of the professed religion. Furthermore, this category of people may be poor in wealth but rich in aesthetic tastes and at the same time in practice.

The results of art from a particular supporting area are the tribes or residents surrounding the area. All levels of society love and protect the preservation of their regional art. For example, a tribe of the Minangkabau people prefers the results of the arts received from their ancestors such as traditional ceremonies. These include raising the head of the leader, festivity, children going down to bathe, and welcoming guests. Furthermore, these arts were followed by plate dance, martial arts competition, countries, captive and folk dances born in their own area, building forms, carving motifs, woven cloths which are decorated with various decorative motifs, etc. Similarly, the other tribes supporting it are a group of people born or raised in the community. However, all of them are in one container, namely, divorced with varying appearance, such as in Indonesia.

Besides the educational environment, the role of artists needs to be re-examined directly by practitioners of fine arts. The artist analyzes the monotonous and unprogressive phenomena without satisfaction, and tries working to display something new with fresh ideas. Due to the creative qualities of these works in terms of ideas, shapes, styles, techniques or colors, some things are not monotonously full of dynamic and progressive. History has proven that the culture of the Indonesian people has been in existence few hundred years ago with high values, admired by Indonesians and outsiders. The results of the nation's culture which is very diverse and varied are a source of inspiration for contemporary artists. Therefore, exploring and studying the culture of the nation itself means participating in preserving, maintaining and upholding the cultural values of the past.

CONCLUSION

Traditional art with high artistic values is the pride of every nation and needs to be protected to avoid extinction. As the dominant savoir, artists support the ideals of Indonesian art by saving the past culture through the transformation of traditional arts into a modern art value that requires awareness of a sense of "Nationalism" in each individual creator. Furthermore, the value of traditional art needs to be relayed into modern form, therefore, it is necessary to have formal education specifically bringing forth beautiful art cadres as torch bearers of traditional art values. These beautiful art cadres can play the role of beautiful art researchers, educators, creators, craftsmen, managers and observers.

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